

A Dilute-Heterojunction Strategy for Probing Charge Generation in Organic Photovoltaics

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Abstract

Recent advances in non-fullerene acceptors (NFAs) have enabled organic photovoltaics (OPVs) to surpass 20% power-conversion efficiency. Despite this progress, the microscopic mechanisms governing efficient charge generation remain incompletely understood, largely due to the complex and highly intermixed morphology of bulk heterojunction (BHJ) blends. Such structural heterogeneity makes it difficult to disentangle key processes such as exciton dissociation, charge-transfer (CT) state formation, and free-charge generation.

To overcome these limitations, this study [1,2] employs dilute donor/acceptor model systems, which provide a significantly simplified and well-controlled morphology. These systems allow direct probing of charge-generation pathways by minimizing phase-separation and reducing structural ambiguity compared to conventional BHJs. Preliminary measurements across multiple NFA/donor systems reveal that charge-generation efficiency strongly depends on the interplay between film morphology, energetic offsets, and the donor/acceptor doping ratio (see figure below).

Additionally, aggregation-driven charge generation is examined in selected NFA blends to evaluate how molecular packing influences early-time photophysics. These results highlight the importance of understanding

morphology-dependent and aggregation-induced charge-generation mechanisms in simplified NFA architectures, offering new insights that can guide the rational design of next-generation high-efficiency OPV materials.

References

References

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NGSE10 conference proceedings (2025) p. 7, Erlangen-Nuremberg, Germany; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18710301>

Figure: The open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) and short-circuit current density (J_{sc} , inset) for the dilute heterojunction OPV for the two NFA systems with the polymer donor.